

Protein production of SLC10A6

ID: SP0015-U

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Protocol description

This protocol is used to purify SLC10A6 expressed in insect cells using detergent solubilization followed by Flag affinity purification, TEV cleavage and size exclusion chromatography

SLC10A6 (Acc. No: Q3KNW5)	
Construct	SLC10A6_302_pD-INS3
Tag ID and position	C-terminal AVI and Flag tag
Cleavage of Tag	No
Sequence SPNS2_301 (In bold primary Protein sequence, C-terminal AVI-Tag (green) - Flag-tag (pink), TEV cleavage site (blue), eGFP (light green))	MANSSEEELPVGLEVHGNLELVFTVVSTVMMGLLMFSLGCSVEIRKLWS HIRRPWGIAGVLLCQFGLMPFTAYLLAISFSLKPVQAIIVLIMGCCPGGT ISNIFTFWVDGMDLSISM TTCSTVAALGMMPLCIYLTWSWSLQQNLT IPYQNIGITLVCLTIPVAFGVVNYRWPKQSKIILKIGAVVGGVLLLVAV AGVVLAKGSWNSDITLLTISFIFPLIGHVTGFLALFTHQSWQRCRTISLE TGAQNIQMCITMLQLSFTAHLVQMLSFPLAYGLFQLIDGFLIVAAYQTY KRRLKKNKHGKKN SGCTEVCHTRKSTSSRETNAFLEVNEEGAITPGPPGP MDCHRALEPVGHITSCEENLYFQGAAGSGEFKGEELFTGVVPIVELDGDVNG HKFSVSGEGEGDATYGKLTLLKFICTTGKLPVPWPTLVTTLTLYGVQCFSRYPDHMK RHDFFKSAMPEGYVQERTISFKDDGNYKTRAEVKFEGDTLVNRIELKGIDFKEDG NILGHKLEYNYN SHNVYITADKQKNGIKANFKIRHNIEDGSVQLADHYQQNTPIG DGPVLLPDNHYLSTQSALS KDPNEKRDHMLLEFVTAAGITHGMDELYKAGLNDI FEAQKIEWHEGDYKDDDDK
Expression System	Sf9 cells
MW	40,990 g/mol (after cleavage)

Materials

Biological materials:	
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1M HEPES, pH7.5 (Applichem, Cat# A6916) ▪ 5M NaCl (Sigma, Cat# S6546) ▪ n-Dodecyl-b-D-maltopyranoside (DDM) (Anatrace, Cat# D310) ▪ cOmplete™, EDTA-free Protease Inhibitor Cocktail (Roche, Cat#04693124001) ▪ Anti-Flag M2 Affinity Resin (Sigma, Cat# A2220) ▪ Flag peptide (Sigma, Cat# F3290-25mg) ▪ TEV (Tobacco Etch Virus) protease (produced in-house) ▪ Superose 6 increase 10/30 GL (Cytiva, Cat#29-0915-96)
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dounce homogeniser ▪ Gravity flow columns ▪ 100 kDa cut-off centrifugal concentrators

Reagents setup

- 5 mg/mL Flag-peptide stock solution (dissolve in 10 mM HEPES, 150 mM NaCl, pH 7.5)

- 10% (w/v) DDM solution in H₂O (leave at 4 °C overnight to allow complete solubilisation and store at -20 °C)

Procedure

Expression

Expression Vector: SLC10A6_302_pD-INS3
Cell line: Sf9
Source: waver expression
Expression duration: MOI 1, 27°C for 72 hours

Purification

Cell disruption by Dounce homogeniser

Affinity purification with Anti-M2 affinity column

Buffer:

- Solubilization buffer: 50mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, Benzoase, complete EDTA free, 1% DDM
- Equilibration/Wash buffer: 50mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 0.026% DDM
- Elution buffer: 50mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 0.026% DDM, 300µg/mL Flag peptide
- SEC buffer: 20mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 0.026% DDM, 10% glycerol

Method:

- Binding, wash with Anti-Flag M2 gravity column
- On-column cleavage with TEV protease to elute SLC10A6 protein
- Temperature: +4°C

Size exclusion chromatography

Buffer:

- SEC buffer: 20mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl, 0.026% DDM

Method:

- Column: Superose 6 increase 10/30 GL
- Flow rate: 0.5ml/min
- Fractions: 0.5ml
- Temperature: +4°C

Size exclusion chromatogram

